

Rurbanization and it's Role in Shaping the Rural Areas Development

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ABSTRACT

Rural areas are the backbone of our country. India live in it's villages i.e Rural areas. With the advent of Industrial revolution in India and LPG (Liberalisation, Privatisation and Globalisation) reforms, the rural areas have been neglected relatively compared to urban areas. The rapid development led to the migration of people from rural to urban areas for labour, employment and other activities. The demographic dividend that India posses is mainly in rural areas. To mitigate the impact of migration from the rural to urban, Rurbanisation plays a key role and sustained growth of our country.

Keywords: Rural, Urban, Rurbanization, Migration, Demographic dividend

INTRODUCTION

The etymology of Rurbanisation is 'Rurban' (Rural+urban) as a geographic territory which possesses the economic characteristics and lifestyles of an urban area while retaining its inherent rural features.

Rurbanization is a slow and invisible process of rural transformation. The magnitude of this transformation may be steady or uneven. Rurbanization process is highly affected by the geographical, political, environmental, and economic constraints and opportunities. Effective implementation of government schemes facilitates the process of rural transformation and thus a vigilant community is a prerequisite for successful Rurbanization process.

OBJECTIVE of interventions in the rural areas is, To improve

- Basic human needs–Health, Education and Employment
- Status of development–Social and Economic
- Improvement in the lives of groups considering the special needs of children, youth, old-age, widows & depressed, disabled and marginalized group.
- Organizing individuals, group and community and creating awareness among them
- Ensuring rural social development through leadership and capacity building
- Improving quality of life.

Rural Development is the key component in the Rurbanization which includes the following,

- Villages with clean environment,
- Beautiful surrounding and having basic amenities with time frame.
- Provide basic amenities(Health, Education)
- Increase employment opportunities.
- Integrate various development schemes.
- Integrate people participation with the development process.

Infrastructure setup in the rural areas like Roads (through Pradhan Mantri Grameen Sadak Yojana), Primary Health Care centre (PHC) and Markets(e-NAM, National Agricultural Market) will make people accessible to the basic amenities and create new employment opportunities for the rural people.

ORIGIN OF PROBLEM

Rural areas which are heavily dependent on primary sector have been neglected in other sectors. A value addition like agro processing industries near the farms has arrived very late. Rural areas have major scope for the development as they are the granaries of the raw material for industries and the educated unemployed. For instance in the guise of Hyderabad the erstwhile districts of Telangana which were rural in nature were neglected. The development in these districts hit back which is the origin for the problem.

STUDY AREA

Rurbanization can be applicable to any of the rural areas of a country or of a state. Telangana is a newly formed state which has many rural villages and has better scope for the Rurbanization.

METHODOLOGY

The study focuses on the surveying socio economic conditions of the study area. The attributes of study area includes quantifying the presence of Approach road, providing drinking water facilities, Construction of primary schoolrooms/anganwadis, Community Halls, Soak-wells / soak-pits, Tree plantation along the main road of the village. An inclusion concept which enables the rural people to participate in basic economic occupation will be studied. Government policies like Shyam Prasad Mukherjee Rurban Mission India which enables the peoples to participate in inclusive modernization to transform in to Rurban will be evaluated.

CONCLUSION

Rurbanization has the ability to shape the socio-economic character of the rural areas. It provides basic amenities which will improve the quality of life people living in rural areas. Enhances the economy of rural area with facilities like banking at doorsteps. Rurbanization has the ability to empower women by providing them better healthcare, employment opportunities and associate them with the outer world. Thus Rurbanization acts the bright spot in rural areas development and contributing to the growth of our country.

REFERENCE

1. Bengs, Christer and Schmidt-Thome, Kaisa (ed.) (2006): ESPON (European Spatial Planning Observation Network) 1.1.2 Final Report on Urban Rural Relations in Europe, Centre for Urban and Regional Studies, Helsinki University of Technology
2. Berdegue, Julio A, Tomas Rosada, and Anthony J. Bebbington (2013) : The Rural Transformation
3. Chatterjee, Sumana (2014): The 'Rurban' Society in India: new facets of Urbanism and its Challenges IOSR Journal Of Humanities And Social Science (IOSR-JHSS) Volume 19, Issue 8, Ver. I (Aug. 2014), PP 14-18
4. Griffon Michel (2002) The Dynamics of Future Development in Rural-Urban Zones: sustainable development for the "rurban" zones?
5. Kumar, Ranjit., Uttam Deb, Cynthia Bantilan, N Nagaraj and M Bhattarai (2014): Economic growth and rural transformation in Eastern India: Strategies for Inclusive Growth,
6. Kundu, Amitabh, Pradhan, Basanta and Subramania, A (2002): Dichotomy or Continuum